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**THE INFLUENCE OF PHYSICIANS AND PARENTS' PERSONALITY TO
DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT OF CHILDREN WITH RESPIRATORY
TRACT INFECTIONS**

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Abstract: respiratory tract infections are widespread among children around the world and are the main reason for seeking primary medical care. The health care management for sick children depends on subjective factors: personalities of physicians, parents (guardians) of sick children, their interaction, expectations, adequacy of risk assessment and benefits of antibiotics' prescribing and over-the-counter medications use, willingness to prescribe and perform necessary diagnostic tests. The paper describes the problem of overuse of antibiotics for the treatment of infections on a global scale. The influence of subjective factors on the organization of diagnosis and treatment of infectious diseases of the respiratory tract in children is demonstrated on the examples of several countries.

Keywords: health care management, respiratory tract infections in children, antibiotic resistance, foreign experience, Macedonia, Australia.

In 2015, WHO announced the Global Plan of Action on Antimicrobial Resistance [1], which was supported by world leaders G7, G20 and the UN General Assembly. The program talks about the global crisis of antibiotic resistance, which threatens the goals of sustainable development. It is proposed to solve the problem on

the basis of a systemic approach, which provides for a simultaneous increase in access to health care with antibiotics (especially for the poor) and the rational use of antibiotics. World consumption of antibiotics increased by 65% between 2000 and 2015, and doubled in the poorest countries. Although more people die in the world today from the unavailability of antibiotics than from antibiotic resistance, improper use of antibiotics is projected to increase the number of untreatable infections without proper intervention, making the treatment of infectious diseases too expensive and difficult. In addition to the rational prescribing of antibiotics by doctors and self-prescribing by patients, it is important to limit the use of antibiotics in agriculture. Today, 70% of total antibiotic consumption is accounted for by livestock and poultry. A rational balance is needed between self-medication, which reduces the burden on the medical system, and the over-the-counter purchase of antibiotics (the latter should be banned). Poor quality and counterfeit (up to 7% according to WHO estimates) antimicrobials increase resistance due to inadequate dosing and unnecessary use of second-line drugs. Today, 60% of countries have national strategies to combat antibiotic resistance [2].

The World Bank estimates that by 2050, antimicrobial resistance could lead to extreme poverty for 28 million people. Lack of water, lack of sanitation and hygiene, which will contribute to the spread of infectious diseases, transmission of antibiotic-resistant infections, and high levels of antibiotics in food and the environment, play an important role in the crisis scenario. By 2050, a quarter of the world's population (excluding Africa) will be over 60 years old, and therefore more vulnerable to infections due to chronic diseases such as diabetes and cancer [3].

The WHO and the UN hope to improve the situation with the antibiotics appointment in primary health care, to involve communities in solving problems and raising public awareness about the proper use of antibiotics, to improve water supply, sanitation and hygiene, to ban the production of irrational fixed doses of antibiotics, to combat antibiotics. drug counterfeiting, restrictions on the use of antibiotics in agriculture (subject to the interests of farmers).

In Alili-Idrizi et al. study (2014) [4], conducted during the year for almost 8

thousand outpatients (children 1–14 years) in the clinic of Tetovo (Macedonia), found that respiratory infections significantly increase the frequency of monthly drug use. The frequency of antibiotic use correlated with the overall frequency of antibiotic use in pediatrics. In addition, seasonal fluctuations in the frequency of use of cephalosporins, macrolides and combinations of antibiotics of two or more groups were noted: more antibiotics were used in the winter months. No seasonal dependence was observed for penicillins. The authors emphasize that up to 80% of antibiotics are used outside hospitals, and their total consumption far exceeds the real need. Especially with the use of antibiotics against viral infections.

Acute respiratory infections in children are associated with the same list of issues in health care management. However, the most interesting experience of high-income countries, where it is possible to investigate the influence of subjective factors (physician and parents/guardians' personality) on the problems of overuse of antibiotics and over-the-counter drugs, as well as the relationship of antibiotics with appropriate bacteriological examination children.

Heward E. et al. (2018) report [5] that in Australia, more than 6 million patients see general practitioners each year for acute respiratory infections, which have a significant impact on public health and economic burden. 70% of the economic costs are borne by hospital caregivers parents (guardians) who care for sick children. Among the listed infections in preschool children (up to 5 years) the most common are acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI), bronchitis/bronchiolitis, acute tonsillitis and pneumonia. For these diseases, patients receive mostly antibiotics and over-the-counter medications (primarily analgesics and cough medicines), which are taken to reduce the severity of symptoms. Parents (guardians) are usually more satisfied with the physician if he prescribes an antibiotic. This fact is also confirmed by observations from the United Kingdom, Canada and the United States. According to the Australian study Bettering the Evaluation and Care of Health (BEACH) conducted in 2007–2021 on more than 4.5 thousand cases of treatment for these pathologies in children under 5 years of age, antibiotics were most often prescribed in the presence of tonsillitis, the least – in the presence of ARVI.

Australia is one of the countries where patients can choose to have an otolaryngologist or a general practitioner of their choice for acute upper respiratory tract infections. In the BEACH study, in 29.6% of cases [95% CI, 28.9÷30.3%], the parents of the patients turned to general practitioners (GP or family doctors). For comparison, the level of visits to GP in such cases in Malaysia and the UK reaches 60%. Prescribing antibiotics and the necessary tests, as well as over-the-counter medications, depended on their gender and age. Among family physicians, antibiotics per 100 requests for medical care for acute infections of the upper respiratory tract were more often prescribed by male physicians [22.5%; 95% CI 20.6÷24.3%] than female physicians [17.2%; 95% CI 15.3÷19.1%]. A comparison of the number of prescribed tests for flora and their sensitivity to antibiotics was also in favor of female physicians: for example, in the presence of tonsillitis, for example, the frequency of prescribed tests per 100 cases was 3.9% among female physicians [95% CI 1.6÷6.3%] and 0.6% among male doctors [95% CI 0.0÷1.3%]. The frequency of prescribing antibiotics per 100 applications was significantly higher among physicians aged 55 years and older [25.4%; 95% CI 22.8÷28.0] than junior physicians [18.0%; 95% CI, 16.4÷19.5]. Over-the-counter drugs per 100 patients with tonsillitis was significantly higher among junior physicians [16.2%; 95% CI 12.3÷20.0] than among physicians older than 55 years [8.0%; 95% CI 4.1÷12.0].

Parents' decisions about hospitalization, the requirement to prescribe antibiotics and taking over-the-counter drugs are influenced by the age and level of education of the parents, the perception of the severity of symptoms. The level of antibiotics in the presence of ARVI is approximately 42% not higher than in other developed countries, but is objectively inflated. Also for comparison, the level of antibiotics in the presence of bronchitis reaches 86%. Excessive prescribing of antibiotics is caused by the expectations/demands of parents (guardians) of prescribing strong drugs in conditions of diagnostic uncertainty in children, as well as insufficient knowledge of physicians about respiratory infections. Education/informing physicians and parents (guardians) to jointly make an adequate decision on antibiotics should help to remedy the situation. Researchers believe that the recommendation of over-the-counter drugs

may reduce parents' demand for unwarranted antibiotics. They also consider it important to improve the diagnostic procedure for infections, because, according to numerous studies, the results of bacteriological tests are often delayed, erroneous or uncertain. The latter factor depends on the skills of medical staff to obtain diagnostic material, a well-established system of material delivery to the laboratory, the management of the laboratory and etc.

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